

BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF 1,3,4-OXADIAZOLE AND THEIR DERIVATIVES: MINI-REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Biologically active compounds play a key role in the fight against diseases affecting both human and animal living organisms, as well as plants. The 1,3,4-oxadiazole has been extensively studied in recent years due to its metabolic profile and ability to engage in hydrogen bonding with receptor sites. 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles and their derivatives show broad and potent activities such as anti-inflammatory, hypoglycemic, anxiolytic, antidepressant, anti-proliferative, antifungal, antibacterial and anti-tuberculosis, anticancer, antimicrobial, anti-HIV, antidiabetic etc., but especially for treating cancer diseases. Substituted 1,3,4-oxadiazoles showed different mechanisms of action and participated in the discovery and development of anticancer drugs. In this article we have summarized various biological activity of 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives in last few decades.

Keywords: Anticancer, Anticonvulsant, Oxadiazole, Antifungal, Antibacterial.

I. INTRODUCTION

A literature study revealed that complex of 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives are valuable compounds. These molecules are widely used in the production of many biopharmaceutical substances, showing a wide range of biological activities.¹ 1,3,4-oxadiazole nucleus is present in various compounds with interesting medicinal properties, especially playing an important role in inducing anticancer activity. In recent years, 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives have attracted considerable attention due to their tumor suppressive properties associated with the inhibition of various growth factors such as enzymes and kinases, histone deacetylase, methionine aminopeptidase, thymidylate synthase, glycokinase, epidermal growth factor, vascular endothelial growth factor, and focal adhesion kinase etc.

1,3,4-oxadiazole is five membered heterocycles possessing one oxygen atom and two nitrogen atoms are considered as 1,3,4-oxadiazole and its derivatives. 1,3,4-oxadiazole can exist in different isomeric forms, they are 1,2,5-oxadiazole, 1,2,4-oxadiazole, 1,2,3-oxadiazole and 1,3,4-oxadiazole. Oxygen and nitrogen containing five-member heterocyclic nucleus is assessed against various diseases. Therefore, they are given important in medicinal chemistry because of their diverse medicinal potential. Substituted 1,3,4-oxadiazole have broad spectrum of biological activities in pharmaceutical and agrochemical field.² 1,3,4-oxadiazole shows wide variety of activities such as virucidal, CNS depressant, genotoxic, anticonvulsant, insecticidal, anti-tubercular, Anti-HIV, herbicidal, anti-inflammatory. It is also known to exhibit anti-malarial, Muscle relaxants, anti tumour, lipid peroxidation inhibitor, antimicrobial, and remarkable analgesic, anticonvulsant, diuretic, hypnotic and sedative properties. There for 1,3,4-oxadiazole is commonly used in the area of new drug development.³ Oxadiazoles belong to the group of heterocyclic compounds which contains one oxygen and two nitrogen atoms, forming a five-membered heterocyclic ring. The oxadiazole molecule is derived from furan, where two carbon atoms are replaced by nitrogen atoms of the pyridine type. Oxadiazole molecules have many properties that are used in various industries. These compounds exhibit a wide spectrum of biological activity, which makes it possible to apply them in medicine and pharmacology as active agents, e.g., with anti-inflammatory and analgesic⁴, antimicrobial⁵, antiviral⁶, antifungal⁷, antitumor⁸ and blood pressure lowering properties.⁹ The antimicrobial properties of 1,3,4-oxadiazoles were the subject of a recent review.¹⁰ Due to the potential biological activity of this type of compound, they are also used in agriculture as herbicides, insecticides and plant protection agents against diseases caused by bacteria, viruses and fungi. The oxadiazole moieties also have valuable optical properties. The 1,2-diazole fragment present in the molecule acts as an electron withdrawing group, so it is widely used in various types of conducting systems.¹¹ It is therefore possible to increase the quantum yield of fluorescence and improve the stability of the molecule. For this reason, oxadiazole derivatives are used as organic light emitting diodes, laser dyes, optical brighteners and scintillators.¹² These molecules can be also found in materials such as thermal insulation polymers.¹³ This review highlights the inhibitory activity of 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives and their structure activity relationship to generate potential biological agents.

II. BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY OF 1,3,4-OXADIAZOLES

2.1 Antimicrobial Activity

The recent emergence of drug resistance when treating infectious diseases has underlined the need for new, safer and more efficient antimicrobial agents. Many researchers have reported excellent antimicrobial activity for compounds containing the 1,3,4-oxadiazole.

Oliveira and co-workers reported the synthesis and antistaphylococcal activity of 1,3,4-oxadiazolines **1** against strains of *Staphylococcus aureus*, resistant to methicillin and aminoglycosides (MARSA) and that encode efflux proteins.¹⁴ The compounds **1** showed efficient antistaphylococcal activity at 4 to 32 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, making all the compounds 2-8 times more active than the standard drug chloramphenicol (Fig.1).

A series of new derivatives of 5-(1-/2-naphthylloxymethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2(3H)-thione (R=SH), 5-(1-/2-naphthylloxymethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-amino (R=NH₂), and 5-(1-/2-naphthylloxymethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2(3H)-ones (R=OH) **2** were synthesized and evaluated for their antimicrobial activity.¹⁵ All were active against *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, *C. albicans* and *C. parapsilosis* at a minimum concentration of 64–256 mg/ML. Patel and Patel verified the antibacterial activity of a series of derivatives containing the 1,3,4-oxadiazole nucleus against Gram-positive (*S. aureus* MTCC 96 and *S. pyogenes* MTCC 442) and Gram-negative bacteria (*E. coli* MTCC 443 and *P. aeruginosa* MTCC 1688) using ampicillin as the drug standard. The compounds 4-[5-(2-chlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl]benzenamine **3** and 3-{[5-(2-chlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl]methyl}-2-{2-[2,6-dichlorophenyl]amino}benzyl}-6-iodoquinazolin-4(3H)-one **4** were respectively 2 and 5 times more potent than ampicillin. 2,5-Disubstituted oxadiazole compounds **5** containing the acetyl group in position 3 of the oxadiazole ring were synthesized and evaluated against two strains of bacteria, *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa*, and against two species of fungi, *C. albicans* and *A. flavus*, by the disk diffusion method. Ampicillin and fluconazole were used as drug standards for the antibacterial and antifungal activity, respectively. In comparison, all of the compounds were equally potent to their ampicillin and fluconazole standards.¹⁶

The antibacterial and antifungal activity of 2-(5-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-4-bromophenol **6**, and 5-(3,5-dibromophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-amine **7** were investigated against two strains of Gram-positive bacteria; *Streptococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, two strains of Gram-negative bacterial; *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Escherichia coli*, and two fungal species; *Aspergillus Niger* and *C. Pannical*. The tests showed activities which were approximately equal to the standard drugs of treatment streptomycin and griseofulvin, respectively.¹⁷

Sangshetti and co-workers investigated the antifungal activity of a number of disubstituted oxadiazoles **8**, each of which contained a triazole unit at position 5 of the oxadiazole ring.¹⁸ The species of fungi tested were *Candida albicans*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus Niger*, and *Cryptococcus neoformans*. Miconazole and fluconazole were used as standards for the comparison. The compounds containing the methyl sulfone (R=SO₂CH₃) group attached to the nitrogen of the piperidine ring, and Cl or OH (R₁) groups exhibited excellent pharmacological profiles (equal to miconazole) against some of the fungi. Compounds **9** and **10** were respectively 2 and 4-fold more potent than fluconazole when evaluated against *E. coli*, and *P. aeruginosa*. Compounds **11** and **12** were twice as potent as fluconazole against *C. albicans*.¹⁹

Fig.1 Disubstituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles with antibacterial and antifungal activity.

2.2 Anticonvulsant Activity

New 3-[5-(4-substituted)-phenyl]-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl]-2-styrylquinazolin-4(3H)-one oxadiazoles **13** were synthesized and evaluated by Kashaw and co-workers for anticonvulsant activity.²⁰ New 2-substituted-5-(2-

benzylthiophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives **14** were designed and synthesized as anticonvulsant agents. The authors found that introduction of an amino group at position 2 of the 1,3,4-oxadiazole ring, and a fluorine substitute at the para position of the benzylthio group improves anticonvulsant activity.²¹ Rajak and co-workers synthesized and evaluated semicarbazones **15** containing the 1,3,4-oxadiazole units for anticonvulsant potential in a three-model test (MES), (scPTZ) and (scSTY).²² Most of them showed activity in all three models. We have also included anticonvulsant activity of other compounds **16-22**.²³⁻²⁸

Fig.2 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles with anticonvulsant activity.

2.3 Anti-inflammatory Activity

A series of oxadiazole derivatives **23** of ibuprofen which contains the arylpiperazine unit at position 3 of the oxadiazole ring were investigated by Manjunatha and co-workers for anti-inflammatory activity using paw edema induced by carrageenan as the method with sodium diclofenac as the reference. Compounds containing 4-Cl, 4-NO₂, 4-F and 3-Cl groups were more active than sodium diclofenac, whereas compounds with 4-MeO and 2-EtO groups showed less activity. Compounds **24** were synthesized from the anti-inflammatory drug fenbufen and evaluated for anti-inflammatory activity by carrageenan induced paw edema; sodium diclofenac and fenbufen were the standards. The compounds containing 4-Cl, 4-NO₂, 4-F and 4-MeO groups were equipotent to fenbufen, and the compound with a 3,4-di-MeO group was more potent than the fenbufen, and equal to sodium diclofenac.²⁹ 2-(1-adamantyl)-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazole compounds **25** displayed strong dose dependent inhibition of carrageenan-induced paw edema with >50% inhibition at a concentration of 60 mg/kg. The compound with the 3,4-di-MeO group was more potent than the indomethacin standard.³⁰ Burbuliene and co-workers investigated anti-inflammatory activity for 5-[(2-disubstituted diamino-6-methylpyrimidin-4-yl)sulphanylmethyl]-3H-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione derivatives **26** and found that some were more potent than ibuprofen.³¹ Other anti-inflammatory activity are also found for compounds **27-34** (Fig. 3).³²⁻³⁹

Fig.3 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles with anti-inflammatory activity.

2.4 Analgesic Activity

5-(2-(2,6-Dichlorophenylamino)benzyl)-N-(4-fluorophenyl)-2-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazole **35** was more potent in an evaluation of its analgesic activity than sodium diclofenac with a maximal analgesic activity of (81,86%) (Fig. 4).⁴⁰ The compound **36** containing the 2,4-dichlorophenyl group, present at the second position of the

oxadiazole ring, showed a maximal activity of $(70.37 \pm 1.67\%)$, almost equivalent to that of the ibuprofen standard $(73.52 \pm 1.00\%)$.⁴¹ Compounds **23**, **24**, **29**, **31**, **32**, **33** (Fig. 3) also display analgesic activity. Compound **24** with the R=4-F group showed a maximal analgesic activity of (72.52%) , better than both sodium diclofenac (70.32%) and fenbufen (54.1%) .

Fig.4 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles with analgesic activity.

2.5 Antitumor Activity

Savariz and co-workers synthesized and evaluated the in vitro antitumor activity of new Mannich bases.⁴² Among the compounds studied, compound **37** showed potent activity against melanoma (UACC-62), and lung (NCI-460) cell lines with GI50 values of 0.88 and 1.01 mmol/L, respectively, in Fig. 5. Liu and co-workers synthesized and reported the anti-proliferative and EGFR inhibition properties of a series of 2-(benzylthio)-5-aryloxadiazole derivatives.⁴³ Compound **38** showed potent biological activity ($IC_{50} = 1.09 \mu M$ for MCF-7, and $IC_{50} = 1.51 \mu M$ for EGFR).

Ouyang and co-workers and Tuma and co-workers synthesized and evaluated various 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives as to their ability to inhibit tubulin polymerization and block the mitotic division of tumor cells.^{44,45} Compounds **39** and **40** exhibited potent activity. In vitro studies of compound **39** indicated that at nano-concentrations it interrupted mitotic division in breast carcinoma and squamous cell tumors, which included multi-drug resistant cells. In vivo studies of compound **40** displayed a desirable pharmacokinetic profile and was significantly more effective than the taxane paclitaxel. The anti-proliferative effects of 24 new 2,5-diaryl-2,3-dihydro-1,3,4-oxadiazoline compounds (Type I) **42**, and (Type II) **43**, analogous to combretastatin-A4 (**41**) were evaluated in murine L1210 leukemia cells, and also in murine B16 melanoma cells. Combretastatin-A4 is the most potent of natural combretastatins. Early studies have shown that it inhibits tubulin polymerization, and proliferation of murine, and human cancer cells. Type I compounds with $R_1=R_2=R_4=R_5=H$, and $R_3=Br$ groups, displayed an IC_{50} of $0.6 \pm 0.7 \mu M$. Type II compounds with $R_1=R_5=H$, and $R_2=R_3=R_4=OCH_3$ displayed an IC_{50} of $0.5 \pm 0.06 \mu M$. However, these compounds were substantially less potent than the compound **41** which displayed an IC_{50} of $0.003 \mu M$ (all for L1210 cells).⁴⁶ Other compounds **44-46** also show antitumor activity.⁴⁷⁻⁴⁹

Fig.5 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles with antitumor activity.

2.6 Antiviral Activity

The US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) on October 16, 2007 approved raltegravir **47**, in Fig. 6 for treatment of human immunodeficiency virus (HIV)-1 infection, in combination with other antiretroviral agents in treatment-experienced adult patients who have evidence of viral replication, and HIV-1 strains resistant to multiple antiretroviral agents. Raltegravir is the prototype of a new class of antiretroviral drugs known as integrase inhibitors.⁵⁰ Seeking to identify more promising compounds than raltegravir, Wang and co-workers

synthesized a series of raltegravir derivatives by modifying the 5-hydroxyl group of the pyrimidine ring and evaluated them for anti-HIV activity.⁵¹ The 5-hydroxyl modification of raltegravir derivatives significantly increased their activity, which indicates the 5-hydroxyl group's dispensability. Compound **48** with a sub-picomol IC₅₀ value was the most potent anti-HIV agent among all of the derivatives synthesized, and thus emerged as a new and potent anti-HIV agent. The inhibitory activity of the compounds **49** and **50** against the human immunodeficiency virus type 1 (HIV-1) was determined using the XTT assay on MT-4 cells. Compound **50** was the most active among the compounds tested, producing 100, 43 and 37% reductions in viral replication at concentrations of 50, 10 and 2 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ respectively. Compounds **49** with R=4-F, and 2-Br groups exhibited less anti-viral replication activity yet above 10% inhibition at concentrations of 2 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. All tested compounds were non-cytotoxic with CD₅₀ > 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ except compound **50** whose CD₅₀ was 68 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.⁵² Iqbal and co-workers reported inhibitory activity for compounds **51** and **52** against the human immunodeficiency virus type 1 (HIV-1) which was also determined using the XTT assay on MT-4 cells.⁵³ Compound **51** with the R=Cl group was the most active among the compounds tested, with 62, 21 and 14% reductions at concentrations of 50, 25 and 5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively.

Fig. 6 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles with antiviral activity.

2.7 Antihypertensive Activity

Hypertension and cardiovascular disease are major causes of morbidity and mortality worldwide. Bankar and co-workers reported the vasorelaxant effect of compound **53**, 4-(3-acetyl-5-(pyridin-3-yl)-2,3-dihydro-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)phenyl acetate, in rat aortic rings by blocking L-type calcium channels.⁵⁴ Bankar and co-workers also investigated whether the correction of endothelial dysfunction is dependent on high blood pressure normalization; in deoxycorticosterone acetate (DOCA-salt), and NG-nitro-L-arginine (L-NNA) in hypertensive rats.⁵⁵ Compound **54** is a T type Ca²⁺ channel inhibitor with an IC₅₀ of 810 nM (Fig.7).⁵⁶

Fig.7 Vasorelaxant activity of 1,3,4-oxadiazoles.

2.8 Enzyme Inhibitors

Leukotrienes (LTs) are potent inflammatory lipid mediators derived from arachidonic acid metabolism, and released from cells involved in inflammation. The synthesis of all LTs requires the action of the enzyme 5-lipoxygenase (5-LO). Inhibition of 5-LO reduces the production of both LTB₄, and cysteinyl LTs (CysLTs); LTC₄, LTD₄ and LTE₄. 5-LO inhibitors have therapeutic potential for the treatment of inflammatory processes. A new oxadiazole p-toluenesulfonate derivative **55** (Fig. 8) containing an asymmetric carbon was identified as both a potent and selective inhibitor of 5-lipoxygenase (5-LO) by Ducharme and co-workers and Gosselin and co-workers.^{57,58} Leung and co-workers reported the discovery of a new class of disubstituted oxadiazoles **56** from oleic acid derivatives with potent and selective inhibition of fatty acid amide hydrolase.⁵⁹ Khan and co-workers performed studies on inhibition effects on tyrosinase with 19 2,5-disubstituted-1,3,4-oxadiazole compounds, the compound 3-(5-(4-bromophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)pyridine **57** with an IC₅₀ of 2.18 μM was more potent than the standard L-mimosine (IC₅₀ = 3.68 μM).⁶⁰ Tomi and co-workers reported a study with the bis-

1,3,4-oxadiazole compound **58** that contains a glycine unit on the transferase activity of enzymes such as: GOT, GPT and γ -GT in serum. Compound **56** showed activation for GOT and GPT and inhibitory effects on the activity of γ -GT.^{61,62}

Fig.8 1,3,4-Oxadiazole as enzyme inhibitors.

III. CONCLUSION

This review article, has summarizes the biological activities of 1, 3, 4-oxadiazole derivatives. From this it is found that the derivatives have verities of activities. Such as anticancer, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, anti-HIV, anti-tubercular, antidiabetic, antifungal and many more. The broad pharmacological profile of this class of compounds is evidenced by the numerous examples cited here. In each biological activity topic, we have only provided selected examples of molecules with relevant activity being that these molecules may serve as prototypes for the development of more active derivatives. So, study on this molecule is useful to the mankind.

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